

Electron micrograph of RGSV 2 particles – 60,000 X.

lengths (see figure). The particles were similar to grassy stunt associated filamentous particles. The ultraviolet absorp-

tion spectrum of the purified fraction was maximum at 260 nm, and minimum at 246-247 nm, which is typical of a nucleo-

Serological reaction of RGSV 1 and RGSV 2 to antisera against RGSV 2 and grassy stunt virus in Japan.

Antiserum	Antigen	Titer of antiserum ^a
RGSV in Japan	RGSV 1	1280
	RGSV 2	640
RGSV 2	RGSV 1	640
	RGSV 2	640

^aReciprocals of the dilution endpoints of the antisera in a precipitin ring interphase test.

protein. The OD 260/280 ratio was 1.29.

Antiserum to RGSV 2 was obtained by immunizing a rabbit with the purified virus. In a precipitin ring interphase test, the titer of the serum against both purified RGSV 1 and RGSV 2 was 1:640. The titer of serum to RGSV in Japan against RGSV 1 and RGSV 2 was 1:1280 and 1:640, respectively (see table). These results confirm a previous report of the close serological relationship between RGSV1 and RGSV 2. □

Unknown virus-like rice disease in Thailand

Somkid Disthaporn, Dara Chettanachit, and Methie Putta, Rice Pathology Branch, Division of Plant Pathology and Microbiology, Department of Agriculture Bangkokhen, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

Stunting and yellowing of rice plants similar to symptoms of yellow orange leaf virus (YOLV) and rice transitory yellowing virus (RTYV) affected dry season rice at tillering stage in Dec 1982 in Ban-Po, Chachoengsao, 60 km east of Bangkok. About 20 to 30% of infected hills were scattered in a field with 60% rice ragged stunt virus (RRSV) infection. About 50 ha planted to Morakot and Kaimookdum were infected by RRSV and the unknown virus. In Mar 1983 the same unknown disease symptoms appeared in an integrated pest control (IPC) experimental field at LumLook-ka, Pratum-thani, 40 km north of Bangkokhen. Infected plants and possible vector insects were counted (Table 1).

Disease symptoms and insect transmission were observed after inoculation of 7-day-old TN1 seedlings. Preliminary insect transmission tests indicated that brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* can

Table 1. Disease-infected plants and insects found in an integrated pest control field, LumLook-ka District, Pratum-thani.

Date	Cultivar	Infected plants				Insects				Plants counted (no.)
		RRSV		Unknown virus		N. lugens		N. virescens		
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	No./plant	No.	No./plant	
24 Mar 1983	RD21	32	7.6	65	15.5	104	.25	0		420
	RD23	2	1	1	0.5	0		0		203
8 Apr 1983	RD7	44	26.7	104	63	102	.62	4	.02	165
	RD21	104	24.2	105	24.4	46	.11	9	.02	430

Table 2. Insect transmission test of unknown disease isolate.

Description of unknown disease	Vector tested	Plants		Symptom
		Total tested	With infection	
Stunted and yellow rice plants resembling those with yellow orange leaf virus disease collected from LumLook-ka, Pratum-thani, Thailand	<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	329	0	
	<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	970	367	Unknown disease
		970	4	Rice ragged stunt virus

transmit the disease (Table 2). Seven days after inoculation, infected plants showed yellowing with interveinal chlorosis. When they became older, chlorosis showed more distinctly. Plants were stunted and some tillered profusely. New

leaves were narrow. With severe infection plants wilted and often died. Some infected plants recovered, but flowering was delayed and they produced poor panicles. □